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Teachers' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Learners in the District of Anini-y, Antique

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Teachers' motivation is likely to be a relevant factor affecting students' learning. This descriptive-correlational study was conducted to determine the Teachers' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Learners in the District of Anini-y, Division of Antique, Philippines for school year 2020-2021 among the 139 teacher-respondents and 180 elementary learner-respondents who were purposively selected to be the participants in this study. The instrument used in this study was adopted from the "Work Motivation Scale" that is used to measure the intrinsic and extrinsic work motivation of teachers developed by Aksoy (2006), being utilized to determine the Teachers' Motivation. Third grading rating of learners for their academic performance was utilized. The findings of the study revealed that the level of teachers' motivation of public elementary school teachers were "High". There are no significant differences in the dimensions when they were classified as to intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. For the level of academic performance of the learner-respondents, it was revealed that the entire group had a very satisfactory performance. There was no significant difference in the level of academic performance of learners in the District of Anini-y. No significant relationship was noted between Teachers' Performance and Motivation.

The schools therefore proposed to increase and improve the performance of learners. Relative to the result of the study, an intervention program in a form of enhancement of teacher's motivation and learners academic performance is designed to address the concerns on improving learners' academic performance.

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